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Don't Wear Your Feathered Hat in the Rain

By Alan Smith

Pianists who collaborate regularly run the gamut from being barely proficient to being absolutely wonderful, from being not naturally flexible to being fabulously adaptable, and from being largely inexperienced in repertoire to possessing a large, varied repertoire. Pianists exist with varying degrees of language skills, from neophyte to having just enough skill to border on being expert. Some know how various instruments and voices make their respective noises; others do not. Some *care* how various instruments and voices make their noises; others do not. The range among those who collaborate measures from resentful servant to domineering tyrant. There is as wide a sweep of personality types as lies in any portion of humanity. Those who work successfully

in the world of collaborative pianism for any length of time learn that the position offers opportunity for a multifaceted life experience. Knowing where you are within that experience, and your adaptability to such knowledge, can greatly enhance your enjoyment of and value to the profession.

We could use the analogy of someone who wears many hats, who is aware of which hat is appropriate at which time, and who desires and is able to change hats quickly and with aplomb. From childhood we learn about hats, their uses, and what they represent. Policemen wear certain hats, as do firemen, nurses, baseball players, football players, religious figures, motorcycle riders, and brides. We learn which hats to wear to keep us warm, to protect us from the rain, and to shelter us from the sun.

There are hats with bands, fringes, feathers, straw hats, felt hats, caps, berets, veils, miters, helmets, chapeaux, bonnets, and crowns.

Within some professions, certain hats are worn at specific times. A policeman might wear one type of hat in the squad car and another when on a motorcycle. A baseball player wears his cap when playing in the outfield, but wears a batter's helmet at the plate. We learn to recognize and expect the appropriate hat for the appropriate profession at the appropriate time. Imagine how quickly our attention would be drawn to a hockey player wearing a bishop's miter.

Figuratively, too, we wear certain hats in various areas of our lives. We may wear the hat of being a parent or other authority figure, or the hat of friend and advisor. We may don the hat of teacher, spy, sports enthusiast, or responsible citizen. We learn which imaginary hats are appropriate to which roles. Some collaborative pianists seem to know instinctively about the appropriateness of the various figurative professional hats. Others sometimes wear their feathered hats in the rain.

Since the middle of this century, accompanying programs have proliferated in American universities, colleges, and conservatories. This has done much to further the fine art of hat-switching. But before this proliferation, and since the inception of accompanying as a viable way to make a living or part of a living, one of the most valuable ways to learn about suitable professional headgear was through personal experience. There is a natural collegial exchange of ideas among those pianists in the profession, and a lively trade in ideas shared among partners from different musical disciplines—singers, string players, wind players, percussionists, dancers, and chorus masters.

What hats does a successful collaborative pianist sport? Some are basic to the wardrobe and ever-present. Among the most important figurative hats in any profession, and collaborative pianists are no exception, is the hat of love for one's subject. This is the genesis of what draws each of us to our particular areas of endeavor. This is the place from which come our enthusiasm and desire to do what it is we do day after day. It is the base for the creative

impulse. The hat of love for one's subject must be an integral part of the wardrobe.

Another hat essential to the wardrobe is the hat of integrity. This attractive chapeau looks good on anyone and possesses very tangible powers. From this point of integrity come all of our thoughts and actions concerning professionalism. This is the realm from which comes the impetus to strive for excellence, to go the extra mile, to achieve distinction. Sometimes, for collaborative pianists, that means staying up a little later, or getting up a little earlier, to practice. It may mean a little more time in the library researching that last fact. It may mean devoting hours over many months to language study. It means doing whatever it takes to achieve professional excellence. These two hats—love for one's subject and integrity—should be worn by all professionals.

Two particular hats that belong to the basic headgear of the collaborative pianist are the hats of perfect ensemble and perfect balance. These are the fundamental tenets of collaborating, and almost everything accomplished by a pianist who performs with others will fall under the brim of one of these hats. Wearing the hat of perfect balance implies, first of all, that the pianist already understands his own craft extremely well and is a superb musician and pianist. Balance is not usually a matter of how loudly or how quietly a performer is playing, but concerns more often matters of tone color, relative projection of a partnering instrument or voice, texture, voicing, clarity of the pianist's bass line, care not to compete with another instrument when doubling a melody exactly, and artful pedaling. Balance also depends on the acoustic of a hall, the basic sound of the piano, the position of the piano, the position of the piano lid, the natural quality of the pianist's tone, and the tone colors of the other partnering instruments or voices.

The hat of perfect ensemble is worn with the knowledge of how other instruments and voices articulate their sounds. String sounds are made mostly with a variety of bowed strokes and pizzicati. Sometimes the bow stroke needs more or less time depending on the length and speed of the bow, the quality of the vibra-

to, the overall dynamic, when and where the bow may change direction, and other related issues. With wind players as well as singers, the time it takes to breathe becomes a crucial matter. Pianists can learn the parameters of breath and how to listen for it. How often I've heard, "She's a wonderful accompanist! She really knows how to breathe!" Pianists will learn that it is possible to hear when a flutist is more than halfway through his air, but not yet more than halfway through the phrase. They will learn how to help the phrase forward at those moments.

To "follow" would be to take an improper role—to wear an inappropriate hat.

The most successful collaborative pianists will also make it their responsibility to know the natures of the various sung languages so that no matter which language is involved, the ensemble will be perfectly aligned with the manner in which that language operates. There are matters of the relative differences between stressed and unstressed syllables, as well as the concept of how many consonants may be grouped together. In Italian, German, and English, for example, the difference between stressed and unstressed syllables is quite noticeable, while the difference in poetically spoken French is not nearly so pronounced.

It is generally agreed among collaborative pianists that when a singer and pianist have notes that are to be sounded simultaneously, the pianist will place the note not with any beginning consonant, but with the first *vowel* sound in the word. If an accompanied word begins with a vowel, "everywhere" for instance, the alignment is immediate and relatively uncomplicated. If the word begins with a consonant or a cluster of consonants, "straight" for

instance, the pianist must allow for the time needed for the singer to sound the consonants before playing exactly with the first vowel. In languages in which consonant clusters are frequent and complex (like German, English, and Russian), the issue of perfect ensemble can be equally complex to learn.

Collaborative pianists who successfully wear the hat of perfect ensemble eliminate the concept of *following* as a viable manner of accompanying and substitute the idea of *playing exactly in conjunction* with another partner. In my own teaching I refer to "following" as "the F word" and refuse to allow students to use it in my presence when referring to collaborating. A popular myth concerning accompanying and its acquired nomenclature assumes that the pianist "follows" the soloist. This is not the case. Ensemble is a mutual responsibility. Truthfully, the pianist often, purely from the number of notes in the piano part compared with those of a partner, has the greater role in motivating the flow of a phrase. To "follow" would be to take an improper role—in that case, to wear an inappropriate hat.

Collaborative pianists, like all pianists and musicians, must learn to switch hats quickly and completely among a variety of musical styles. Those pianists who play with singers have the added responsibility of dealing directly with the meaning of words and the nature of various languages. Some pianists learn to play quite successfully within the style of Germanic romanticism and receive praise for their ability to play musically within that genre. The mistake many make is to leave the German romantic hat on their heads when they move to French impressionism or other styles. They may try to play a song of Fauré in the same style in which they play a Brahms intermezzo or Schumann violin sonata. They must learn to make distinctions among the styles of various periods, geographical boundaries, and language traits. They must know how to recreate orchestral colors when playing piano reductions of concerto and aria accompaniments. The best collaborative artists learn to change hats completely and quickly among the textures, fabrics, and colors of various styles.

One of the clearest and most interesting laboratories in which to observe

quick hat-switching occurs when a student pianist accompanies a lesson, especially a voice lesson. While most professional pianists do not make a living accompanying for lessons, this is where many learned their trade. Often in a voice lesson there is no verbal cue, or cue of any kind, when the pianist might be expected to switch hats. It must be intuited. Very often also the focus is not on the ultimate musical payoff as the immediate end, but in exploring the steps to get there. If the pianist wears only his Horowitz-playing-at-Carnegie-Hall hat at the lesson, he faces probable artistic frustration, because reality will not match expectation. Instead, if he switches among hats more appropriate to the moment, his success, enjoyment, and effectiveness will be greatly enhanced. Other hats he might wear, and among which he may have to switch quickly, are the hat of experimentation through repetition, the hat of developing the ear to hear subtle distinctions in vocal timbre, the hat of patience, the hat of cooperation, the hat of pitchgiver (giving a needed pitch at just the right time in just the right way without being asked), and the hat of training the ear to gauge how to breathe with a singer. And yes, sometimes he *will* be expected to play like Horowitz in Carnegie Hall.

Pianists who accompany in the lesson situation may afterward feel like a library book that, after it has been read, is dumped down a chute. As a teacher of collaborative pianists, I hear all kinds of expressions of discontent from pianists who feel it is drudgery to accompany in lessons. I also hear from teachers and the students for whose lessons pianists play about the lack of success and misunderstandings that can arise from not knowing about and wearing the various hats needed by collaborative pianists in the lesson situation. With just a little bit of knowledge and the application of it, many challenges could be dealt with more effectively. It is crucial, particularly when so challenged, that pianists and those with whom they work realize and remember the necessity for excellence. They must be excellent for the sake of the music, for the sake of their own reputations, for the well-being of their musical partners, and purely for the practical consideration of marketability in a pro-

fession that is growing in numbers and quality.

Sometimes collaborative pianists will wear the hat of amateur advisor in extra-musical matters related to personality and emotion. Music-making can be a very revealing discipline psychologically. Some wear the advisor's hat well; some do not. Some are happy to wear this hat; others avoid it at all costs. Knowing when, where, and whether one is able to wear this hat becomes an intriguing aspect of the collaborative experience. Few things are more unwelcome than a little psychiatric evaluation from the

wrong person at the wrong time.

Another hat is that of musical coach. Collaborative pianists tend to divide on this issue through a process akin to natural selection. The manner in which the profession has developed in this century has created the circumstance within which pianists who play primarily with singers are usually expected to coach as well. Pianists who play primarily with instrumentalists are not usually expected to coach that instrument or repertoire. So-called vocal coaches are often experts (or wish they were) in matters of language diction and translation, reper-

Piano faculty member Mack McCray with pianist Mimi Park (Music Diploma '96)

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toire selection, stylistic points, vocal production, and other interpretive issues. Most vocal *coaches* do not wear the hat of vocal *teacher*, though there are a few who do it well. Some coaches think they are fine vocal teachers, but truly are not. Choosing whether or not to wear a “coach” hat is in part decided for collaborative pianists through the manner in which the profession has developed. Those who purposely decide to wear this hat must know when and where it is appropriate, and must also be able to wear the hat very well.

Situations arise in which a pianist functions as a vocal coach in preparation for a recital, and then collaborates with the singer in the performance. Many find this hat-switching from coach to performer tricky. When a pianist coaches, he listens in a different way than when he is there to accompany but not to coach. The division of the listening attention is different. When coaching, less attention is usually given to the playing of the piano and more to the qualitative sounds coming from the singer. In a performance, more of the

pianist’s attention is directed to the actual playing, and the portion of the brain attending to the singer normally involves listening for issues of ensemble, rather than listening qualitatively for issues of language, style, and tone color. Such hat-switching can be touchy, and more than one pianist has had to learn the hard way.

I had a doctoral student in collaborative piano who was a superb musician and pianist, and also a very fine coach. In planning one of his doctoral recitals he chose, with great care and enthusiasm, the repertoire, venue, date, and perfect singing partner for his dream recital. He researched the composers, the poets, and the texts. He carefully prepared the diction of the various languages involved in order to be an effective language coach. He met often with his singing collaborator to rehearse the recital in great detail. He also practiced very hard himself and grew wonderfully in the preparation of the program. On the evening of the recital, all was in place. Everyone anticipated a fine performance. The partners swanned on to the stage. Everything in the first song was going well until the pianist had a glitch in concentration. At that point, a few very interesting, very wrong, notes came sailing out into the hall. I cringed inwardly, knowing the feeling all too well. There can be many causes for such a lapse (nerves being one), but the pianist was experiencing, among other things, the challenge many collaborative pianists face in making the switch from wearing the coach’s hat to wearing the performer’s hat. The remainder of that group of songs and the rest of the recital went swimmingly, with the shock of the hat-switch-polka rearing its ugly head only infrequently.

The craft of collaborative pianism touches tangentially on many issues. Each of those issues, it could be said, demands that the pianist wear a different hat, or combination of hats. The most successful collaborative pianists discover which hats are needed and desired, and see to it that they have those hats in their wardrobes. They pay careful attention to determine which hats are appropriate to which situations and wear these different hats joyously and proudly. And they don’t wear feathered hats in the rain. ❖

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